

Factors of Tax Evasion in Laghman Province, Mihterlam City

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Abstract:

This study explores the causes of tax evasion in the Mihterlam City, Laghman province. The study aims to identify the factors contributing to tax evasion, highlight the most significant ones, and differentiate between those that increase or decrease evasion. This qualitative descriptive research involved interviews with 19 businessmen from Mihterlam city. The interview questions reviewed for accuracy by Laghman University's Scientific Research Committee. The study identified seven key factors influencing tax evasion: high tax rates, public awareness of taxes, income levels of

businesses, administrative corruption, and literacy levels of business owners, the behavior of tax collectors, and the use of technology in tax collection. High tax rates, corruption, poor behavior of tax collectors, and income levels were found to directly increase tax evasion. Conversely, greater public awareness, higher literacy levels, and the use of advanced technology in tax collection were found to indirectly reduce tax evasion.

Keywords: *Tax, Tax Evasion, Government Revenue, Public Finance.*

Introduction

Countries around the world need economic development, growth, and stability. They are responsible for providing and financing public services such as infrastructure, healthcare, education, security, and other essential functions. The Islamic Emirate of Afghanistan also manages a number of limited resources to finance public services. Among these resources

are taxes, leases, revenues from air and ground transportation, various license fees, fines, revenues from the diplomatic sector, customs tariffs, civil affairs, and many other sources.

Laghman province is one of Afghanistan's provinces where taxes serve as a main source of government revenue. Taxes are payments imposed on the income and assets of individuals. Essentially, tax is a mandatory contribution that

citizens pay to the government without receiving proportional services in return, as dictated by law. Unfortunately, taxes in our country are not collected as effectively as required by law. Taxes are as vital to a government as blood is to a human being. They are compulsory financial charges imposed on individuals or legal entities by the government to cover public expenses.

Some describe taxes as mandatory payments levied by the government without providing direct individual compensation for specific goods or services. A tax is a compulsory financial charge or levy imposed by a government agency to fund various public expenditures. As mentioned, taxes are crucial for running the affairs of any government, and every businessperson or individual whose income or assets are subject to taxation has a responsibility to submit their taxes to the tax authority. However, many businessmen evade paying taxes, which leads to a significant decrease in government revenue. Tax evasion is a major social problem that hinders the development process in developing countries. Most tax evasion occurs in the shadow economy—an economy where people do not disclose their true income or engage in illegal practices to avoid paying taxes.

It is important to distinguish between tax evasion and tax avoidance. Tax evasion refers to illegally hiding taxable income or underreporting it to tax authorities, while tax avoidance involves legally reducing one's tax liability by using legitimate methods. As taxes are very important for financing the government budget and running the day-to-day affairs of the government, a decrease in taxes leads to a decrease in government revenue and creates a budget deficit due to which a government may face with many problems and difficulties. That tax evasion causes a decrease in public service financing resources, which eventually weakens the government's ability to provide public services. It is necessary to develop it in order to identify the factors of tax evasion in Laghman province in Mihterlam city, to consider the government in making policies to prevent it.

Materials and Methods

This study, titled "Factors of Tax Evasion in Mihterlam City, Laghman Province," is a qualitative descriptive research. The study focuses on the businessmen of Mihterlam city. For data collection, first-hand data was gathered through interviews. We conducted 19 interviews, reaching a **saturation** point, so the sample size is 19. The interview questions were reviewed and approved by the professional board of the Central Research Committee of Laghman University to ensure accuracy. Data analysis was carried out using thematic analysis. The collected data were organized and presented in tables for analysis.

Significance of the Study

Revenue is essential for the operation and survival of governments. Changes in revenue—whether an increase or decrease—show imbalances in a country's fiscal policy. If government revenue rises too much, it can lead to a budget surplus, while a decrease can result in a budget deficit. Both extremes are undesirable. Governments aim to keep their budgets balanced and use different methods to achieve this. As mentioned earlier, one key source of government revenue is taxes, which many countries rely on more than other sources. A drop in tax revenue reduces government income, often due to tax evasion and non-payment of taxes. This research seeks to identify the factors that contribute to tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province. The findings can help policymakers develop better tax policies to reduce tax evasion and increase government revenue. This, in turn, will help the government better fund public services. Additionally, there is limited research available on financial issues in national languages. This study will provide useful information for employees, students, and anyone interested in this field.

Objectives

- To identify the factors contributing to tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province.

- To highlight the most and least important factors of tax evasion in Mihterlam city, using qualitative analysis.
- To distinguish between factors that have a direct or inverse relationship with tax evasion.

Research Questions

- What are the causes of tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province?
- Among the factors contributing to tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province, which ones are of high importance and which are of low importance?
- Which factors are directly related to tax evasion, and which ones have an inverse relationship?

Literature Reviews

Various studies on tax evasion have conducted in different countries, and research on this topic continues. However, in Afghanistan, especially in national languages, very few studies have conducted on this subject. To help fill this gap, this research has been undertaken. Afghanistan, like many developing countries, has limited financial resources compared to its expenses. As a result, it heavily depends on internal revenues like taxes. Developing countries often prioritize tax collection, which can lead to tax evasion, as mentioned in previous studies.

Mughal (2012) researched tax evasion in Pakistan. The Data was collected through questionnaires, revealing that factors such as a lack of public awareness, low motivation to pay taxes, poor relationships between taxpayers and authorities, high tax rates, and an unfair tax system contribute to tax evasion. Similarly, Khan and Waseem Ahmad (2014) surveyed 100 students in Bahawalpur, Pakistan. They found that factors such as a corrupt government, high tax rates, and the influence of other non-taxpayers were significant causes of tax evasion.

Kamal (2019) conducted a study in Pakistan using data from 400 salaried employees. The study examined four factors: guilt, trust in the government, perception of other taxpayers, and

penalties. The results showed that perceptions of government spending, shame, the behavior of other taxpayers, and penalties influenced tax evasion. However, blaming government corruption did not significantly affect tax evasion.

Şuvelea (2014) categorized the causes of tax evasion into four groups: moral, political, economic, and technical. Neifar (2016) studied tax evasion in Tunisia, surveying 101 students. The results indicated that medical students and women were more opposed to tax evasion than others. Annan & Friends (2014) found that per capita income, average tax rates, age, and inflation were positively related to tax evasion, while gender had an inverse relationship.

Richardson (2006) studied multiple countries and found that non-economic factors, like the complexity of the tax system, had a greater impact on tax evasion than economic factors. Important factors included education, income source, fairness, and fiscal ethics. Richardson & Sawyer (2001) highlighted that middle-income earners were more likely to agree with paying taxes, while low- and high-income earners were less compliant. Gender also played a role, with men being less willing to pay taxes than women.

Mansor (2016) studied tax evasion in Gombe State, Nigeria. The results showed that the tax system, income level, and education were positively related to tax evasion. It was suggested that measures should be taken to fight corruption, raise public awareness, and improve the tax process.

Jackson & Milliron (1986) identified 14 key factors influencing tax evasion, including age, gender, education, employment status, income level, tax complexity, fear of taxes, communication with tax authorities, and tax-paying morale. They noted that higher education could lead to better understanding and compliance with tax laws. Wallschutzky (1984) found that tax evasion is more common in regions where traditional work like agriculture dominates.

Oz Yalama & Gumus (2013) found additional factors influencing tax evasion, such as tax

audits, penalties, public spending, misunderstandings about taxes, and bureaucracy. Sandmo (2005) emphasized that a fair tax rate, penalties, and audits could help reduce tax evasion, as these decisions are ultimately up to individual taxpayers.

Oduro et al. (2018) used a cross-sectional survey to explore what factors influence taxpayers to evade taxes. They found that traditional and institutional factors had a positive effect on tax evasion, while socio-cultural factors like gender, income, education, and age had little effect. Miskama et al. (2013) studied tax evasion in imported cars in Malaysia and identified factors such as tax rates, penalty structures, car brands, and the business size of car importers.

Results

Tax evasion is the intentional and illegal avoidance of paying taxes, such as false reporting of income, overstating expenses or deficits, concealing assets, using fake and illegal accounts, etc. Tax evasion has negative consequences for both individuals and society, such as reduced public services, increased inequality, reduced

trust in the government, and the creation of grounds for corruption, among others. Like the rest of the world and especially in other provinces of Afghanistan, there are many factors of tax evasion in Mihterlam city of Laghman province. The level of income, administrative corruption, the attitude of tax collectors, the level of literacy of entrepreneurs, the lack of new techniques and technology in the tax collection system were mentioned. One of the main reasons mentioned above is the high tax rate. There are many ideas behind why the high tax rate has led to the escape of the businessmen from taxes, which have received different answers from the interviewees during the interview. The list of these answers includes the lack of sales, the inability to pay taxes, the decrease in the profits of businesses, the unproportioned burden of taxes with the level of businesses, the fear of the destruction of businesses, the lack of public awareness, the expenses of businesses. The height, the indifference of the taxpayers to the law and the lack of information about the documents on which the collected taxes are spent have caused the taxpayers to evade paying taxes.

Table.1 High Tax Rate

No.	Participants' opinion	Participants code
1	People do not have general knowledge about taxes.	1, 5
2	Increase in business expenses.	14, 15
3	People do not know in which places their taxes are spent.	1
4	The tax rate is not proportional to the level of business.	2,12,13
5	Businessmen are unable to pay taxes.	3, 4, 5, 7, 18, 19
6	Entrepreneurs ignore the law.	5
7	A high tax rate can cause business to collapse.	6, 9, 10
8	Decreased sales of businesses.	7, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17
9	Decreased business profits.	8, 11, 14, 15

Another major factor contributing to tax evasion in Laghman province is the lack of public awareness and misconceptions about taxes. Many people believe that operators lack understanding about taxes, which leads to evasion. Interviews revealed that some businessmen who pay taxes think their money goes into officials' private pockets. They are

often unaware of how tax revenue is used, the benefits and importance of taxes, and view tax payments as a personal loss. Additionally, taxes are sometimes seen as a form of coercion by authorities, and the low level of education among operators is also cited as a reason for tax evasion.

Table 2. Lack of Public Awareness and Miss Understanding about Tax Collection

No.	Participant's opinion	Participant code
1	Not understanding the usage of taxes.	1, 9, 14, 17, 19
2	People think that paying taxes is just their personal loss.	1, 14
3	Taxpayers believe that their taxes go into the personal pockets.	2, 3, 6, 7, 8, 16, 18, 19
4	They did not know the benefits and advantages of taxation.	3, 4, 5, 17
5	Not understanding the purpose of tax collection.	6, 9
6	Not understanding the importance of tax.	7, 13
7	Lack of tax information.	9, 10, 11
8	Taxes are considered a form of coercion.	10, 12
9	Low level of education or literacy of business owners.	16

One factor contributing to tax evasion is the low level of revenue or sales. Interviews revealed that individuals with high incomes evade taxes because they face higher tax rates. On the other hand, those with low incomes may avoid taxes because paying them would reduce their already limited income. Factors such as increasing tax

rates, and having power and influence, also contribute to tax evasion. People at all income levels tend to avoid taxes because paying them decreases their income, leading to higher rates of tax evasion among high-income earners compared to others.

Table 3. Income Level of Tax Payer's

No.	Participant's opinion	Participant code
1	Having more income.	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10, 11, 13, 18, 19
2	Having strength, power and influence.	1, 9, 19
3	An increase in the percentage and volume of taxes.	1, 4, 6, 7, 8, 9, 13
4	Having a moderate income.	3, 5, 10
5	Having a low income.	2, 3, 5, 10, 11, 12, 14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19

Another factor contributing to tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province, is corruption. Interviews revealed that businessmen often reduce their tax liabilities through bribes. Corruption in the tax collection process leads to the belief that taxes are diverted into the pockets of tax officials, making tax

payments seem unnecessary. This corruption decreases people's trust in the government, undermines the enforcement of tax laws, and fosters the perception that paying taxes supports corruption. Additionally, inequitable taxation, a poor tax system, and the lack of incentives for businessmen also contribute to tax evasion.

Table 4. Administrative Corruption

No.	Participant's opinion	Participant code
1	People think that paying tax is like taking part in corruption.	1
2	Tax volume is not in proportion with business volume.	2, 7,
3	Existence of relationship and bribes.	2, 6, 8, 10, 11, 17
4	Non-enforcement of laws.	5
5	Lack of good fiscal system.	5
6	Lack of public trust in the government.	7, 19
7	Failure to observe justice and equality in the imposition of taxes.	9
8	The presence of corruption creates the perception that taxes go into the personal pockets of tax-collecting officials, and that tax payments are unnecessary.	12, 18
9	Lack of government support for business owners.	15

Another factor contributing to tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province, is the poor behavior of tax collectors. Interviews revealed that negative interactions with tax collectors are a major reason for tax evasion. Many respondents noted that unprofessional conduct by tax collectors, such as sealing shops or imposing fines, drives business owners to evade taxes. The dissatisfaction with tax collectors'

treatment can lead to the closure of businesses. However, some participants felt that the behavior of tax collectors does not significantly affect tax evasion, arguing that tax amounts are fixed and the government enforces them. Despite this, the consensus was that poor behavior by tax collectors does contribute to tax evasion.

Table 5. Bad Behavior of Tax Collection Officials

No.	Participant's opinion	Participant code
1	Misbehavior by tax collectors leads to tax evasion.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, 10, 11, 12, 18, 19
2	Tax collectors cannot satisfy taxpayers.	1, 12, 15
3	The sealing or fine of the shop by the tax collector creates tax evasion.	2, 8, 16
4	Bad attitude of tax collectors leads to closure of business.	6, 9, 16
5	Tax evasion occurs if the flexibility is used.	7
6	Tax evasion does not occur if it is used wisely.	7
7	Ethics and attitude have no effect because the amount of tax is fixed and the government collects it compulsorily.	13, 17

One significant factor affecting tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province, is the level of literacy among businessmen. Interviews revealed varying opinions on how literacy affects tax evasion. Most respondents believed that low literacy among business owners contributes to tax evasion because literate owners understand the value and benefits of taxes and are more

likely to pay them. However, a few respondents argued that high literacy might also lead to tax evasion. Some interviewees considered taxes as a legal obligation that should not be influenced by literacy levels. Overall, it can be concluded that low literacy among businessmen is a major factor leading to tax evasion.

Table 6. Education Level of Businessmen

No.	Participant's opinion	Participant code
1	The literate class does not escape from it because they know the value and advantages of taxation.	1, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14
2	The illiterate class or those with low literacy levels escape from it.	1, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15, 16, 17
3	The illiterate does not know its value and benefits.	1, 2, 4, 7, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 19
4	Lack of tax information.	2, 5, 12
5	It is assumed that this money goes into private pockets.	2, 12
6	Taxation is considered a form of coercion.	6, 19
7	The literate escapes from it because he knows the ways of taxation.	9
8	The illiterate does not escape from it.	9
9	Literacy or illiteracy has no effect on tax payment.	18, 19

Another factor contributing to tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province, is the lack of modern technology and techniques in the tax collection process. Interviews revealed that

issues such as tax corruption, lack of transparency, and inaccurate tax measurement are related to the absence of advanced technology. It was concluded that the failure to

use new technologies and techniques in tax collection contributes to tax evasion in Laghman province.

Table 7. Lack of New technology and Procedures

No.	Participant's opinion	Participant code
1	The problem of tax assessment.	1, 5
2	Tax evasion is prevented by using new technology.	1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 10, 11, 12, 13, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19
3	Problems arise in tax collection.	1, 5, 18
4	Creating non-transparency.	7, 13
5	Tax corruption occurs.	9, 13, 15, 17

Discussion

The research on tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province, has uncovered several key factors influencing tax evasion, which are consistent with and expand upon existing literature. High tax rates emerged as a significant factor in tax evasion, aligning with findings from Khan & Ahmad (2014) and Mughal (2012), who both emphasized that increasing tax rates can drive individuals to evade taxes to protect their income. The study confirmed that high tax rates create an incentive for tax evasion, as individuals seek to avoid the financial burden. The lack of public awareness about taxes was also identified as a major factor contributing to tax evasion. This finding corroborates Mughal (2012), who found that insufficient public awareness campaigns lead to higher tax evasion. Kamal (2019) further supported this by noting that a lack of motivation to pay taxes, stemming from inadequate awareness, results in non-compliance. Income levels of taxpayers were found to influence tax evasion, with both low and high-income earners affected. High-income earners were particularly noted to evade taxes more frequently. This observation is consistent with the work of Richardson & Sawyer (2001) and Mansor (2016), who highlighted that income levels significantly impact attitudes toward tax compliance. Administrative corruption was another critical factor identified, reducing trust in the tax system and encouraging evasion. This finding aligns with Kamal (2019) and Oduro et al. (2018), who noted that corruption fosters a perception that taxes are misappropriated,

diminishing taxpayer confidence. The behavior of tax collectors also played a role in tax evasion, as negative interactions with collectors led to increased evasion. This result is consistent with Jackson & Milliron (1986), who pointed out that poor communication and treatment by tax officials can drive taxpayers to evade taxes. The research revealed that lower literacy levels among businessmen are linked to higher tax evasion. This finding supports Richardson (2006), who found that education and literacy levels impact tax compliance. Business owners with lower literacy may lack understanding of the benefits of taxation and the requirements for compliance. Finally, the study highlighted the non-use of new techniques and technology in tax collection as a factor contributing to tax evasion. This observation reflects Richardson's (2006) findings that technological advances can enhance transparency and efficiency in tax collection, reducing opportunities for evasion. Overall, the research on tax evasion in Mihterlam city corroborates and builds on existing literature by highlighting that high tax rates, lack of public awareness, income levels, administrative corruption, behavior of tax collectors, literacy levels, and technological advancements all significantly influence tax compliance. Addressing these factors comprehensively could lead to improvements in tax collection and reductions in tax evasion in the region.

Conclusion

Tax evasion remains a critical issue, particularly in developing countries, where it significantly impacts both individuals and broader society. This research reveals that several key factors contribute to tax evasion in Mihterlam city, Laghman province. High tax rates, administrative corruption, inappropriate behavior by tax collectors, and the income levels of business owners have been identified as direct drivers of tax evasion. These elements contribute to a reduction in government revenue, complicating the process of financing essential public services and stalling economic progress.

In addition to these direct factors, the study highlights that public awareness about taxes, the literacy levels of business owners, and the use of technology and new techniques in tax collection play an indirect role in tax evasion. Improved public awareness and higher literacy levels among business owners, alongside the integration of modern technology in tax collection, are associated with reduced tax evasion. Therefore, addressing these indirect factors can contribute to a decrease in tax evasion, while tackling the immediate issues of high tax rates, corruption, and collector behavior is essential for more intervention that is direct.

Overall, a multifaceted approach that includes enhancing public awareness, improving literacy, modernizing tax collection processes, and addressing corruption and excessive tax rates is crucial for effectively combating tax evasion and ensuring a more robust fiscal system.

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